

Attractive colours and clean lines of these OS pots prove a winner with customers.

Potting along with OS

We are very pleased that our thoughts on the suitability of the OS range of thermoformed pots tie in so closely with actual nursery requirements.

Most nursery pots are required to last only a single planting cycle before ending up in a dump. OS pots are significantly thinner plastic, thus reducing the amount of plastic (and energy) used in each cycle, allowing for better prices. The thermoforming process allows pots to be made with a very thin wall.

The manufacturing method using a co-extruded plastic, gives the option of a black interior (to keep light away from active root tips), while being able to have a preferred colour on the outside. Our standard range uses a very attractive terracotta colour.

Other features useful in the nursery are the incorporation of universal drainage (can be used on all types of nursery benching, including capillary mat), and the precision moulding means these pots do not jam on automatic pot de-stackers.

Setting very small radiata cuttings into containers for rooting on bottom-heat. Each hand-pollinated seed can result in many plantation trees with improved genetic potential.

Setting a Rapid pace

Plugs and plugging have proved a major advantage in the bedding plant industry. The availability of economical and reliable plug transplanting machinery has resulted in significant savings at many nurseries.

The Rapid range of plug transplanters is readily set up and altered between the commonly used combinations of plug trays and flats or pots. The precision grip and spacing mechanism ensures accurate placement and a minimal requirement for patching finished flats.

A large version in the Rapid range of plug transplanters for high-speed planting of bedding plant plugs.

Chilean pine ideas

On a recent visit to Chilean forest nurseries, I was interested to see that their containerised seedling and cuttings programme was highly advanced.

Containerised stock is strongly preferred for planting in the more difficult sites - especially if dry soils are likely to be encountered. Virtually all the companies were planning to change to containerised stock for their own plant requirements, keeping on the bare-root nursery for general plant sales.

Growing radiata cuttings from intensively managed seedlings and setting them into the final container with rooting done in heated greenhouses was becoming a common practice. This method optimises the still-scarce hand-pollinated seed of improved varieties, combined with the benefits of containerised stock. They want to get new genetic material into their plantations as soon as possible.

2020 Vision in sight?

The remarkable increase in Australian plantations over the past two years, with projections for this 2001 planting season indicating a further bumper planting season, has brought quite considerably the likely date to achieve the 2020 Vision.

By far the biggest programme has been establishment of new plantations of *Eucalyptus globulus* (Tasmanian blue gum) and *E. nitens* (shining gum). Significant funds for these plantations have been derived for many years from the traditional sources, forestry and paper companies securing the supply of their input resources. More recently, significant funds have been derived from investment sources (through so-called prospectus companies). Some of these plantations have been pre-sold to paper and other timber product manufacturers, while others will be sold on the open market at time of harvest. Either way, these new plantations are changing the face of the countryside, and in some instances bringing people back into rural areas of Australia.

A Eucalyptus nitens seedling ready for a plantation, with millions more behind it. Lannen seedling tray technology has been widely endorsed by the major nurseries and plantation managers of Australia.

Actual plantation estate (National Plantation Inventory data), with our projections based on a continued increase in the rate of expansion, or continued new planting at the current rate.

2020 in a nutshell

The Vision, a creation of the Australian Department of Primary Industries and Energy, was to triple the plantation estate from 1.1 million hectares in 1996 by the year 2020.

The primary means of achieving this has been to create an investment climate suitable for attracting private funds, and secondly to assist in the planning and development of further downstream processing investments.

To many, plantation forestry is seen as a hostile, arrogant use of land. Eucalypt chip has proved an excellent material for many consumer products, particularly paper. With those same consumers demanding that native stands of Eucalypts be preserved, an increasing divergence in the value of these stands has occurred. To maintain this renewable source of a valuable commodity, plantations (or tree farms, possibly a more descriptive term) are the answer.

Two other factors come into play in the change of land use from so-called "traditional" purposes of pastoral and agricultural cropping. Both of these uses have resulted in significant salinity increase in soils and rivers. The answer is to increase the number of trees growing in a catchment in order to lower the water table, and with it the salt levels. In addition, tree farming is currently giving a far better return on land use.

Step up to our superior cell - but keep your current footprint!

A new Lannen tray is now available for perennial plant propagation. This tray incorporates all the quality features of Lannen trays, including sculpted cell architecture with root-pruning side slots, and air-flow ventilation holes.

The Lannen 64AF tray fits within the common Australian underlay size of 292 x 345 mm. Cells are 62mm deep and 66ml volume. Anticipated nursery uses are seedlings for blue gum plantation, oil mallees and saltbush.

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